
**SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THE ELECTRONIC FORM OF
EDUCATION USING "INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION
TECHNOLOGIES" UNDER THE CONDITIONS OF GLOBAL
DIGITALIZATION.**

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Annatation.

The article examines the use of information and communication technologies in the education system in the context of the rapid development of information processes in the world. Using e-learning resources when using information and communication technologies in traditional education, using effective teaching methods such as online learning courses, distance learning, mobile learning, e-learning. Online educational resources are widely used in teaching full-time and part-time students, self-study, and advanced training.

Key words.

Blended education, information and communication technology, online education, self-directed learning, distance learning, e-learning.

While informatization processes in the world are developing at a tremendous speed, the use of information and communication technologies in the education system has become an urgent need. Effective use of information and communication technologies and the use of electronic educational resources in traditional education.

Online learning courses, distance learning, mobile learning, e-learning are used as teaching methods, which are widely used and effective in Russia, Europe and Korea. Online educational resources are widely used in teaching full-time and part-time students, independent students, advanced training.

As a result of the use of electronic educational resources using information and communication technologies in traditional education, the concept of blended learning (Blended Learning) was created in modern education. Blended learning [1,3] - the student receives new knowledge from the teacher and online resources.

In this case, the student will be able to control the pace, time and quality of knowledge.

The blended learning system can be used in corporate training of schoolchildren, students, employees and various trainings.

In blended learning, the student first learns new knowledge from the teacher in the classroom, and after training improves and consolidates his knowledge by doing homework using electronic resources.

Teachers can assign students labs, seminar quizzes, topic questions, or self-study on a topic as homework. Internet resources, in turn, are enriched with control questions that track students' knowledge, control the pace and quality of student learning.

Here are the pros and cons of blended learning:

Students have a number of benefits for learning using online learning resources:

1. A student voluntarily begins to study on an educational resource. The student develops self-control, striving for the goal;

2. The student can study at a convenient time and in convenient conditions. He can learn new knowledge and professions with the help of online courses, without going anywhere for additional knowledge.

All you need is a computer and the Internet;

3. Students' learning is accelerated through training courses created on the basis of multimedia (video, audio, animation) elements, this technology is especially effective for intensive study of foreign languages;

Disadvantages of blended education:[2,89]

1. Students, independent learners do not have the skills to use an online educational resource;

2. Lack of opportunities for students to use online courses. There is not enough computer or the Internet is not connected;

3. Teachers, educators do not have sufficient knowledge on the creation and use of courses;

4. Lack of programmers who create software for online educational resources and specialists who accompany them.

Suggestions and recommendations. We believe that in order to address the above shortcomings, it is necessary to provide adequate funding for the necessary technical support and professional guidance for staff and students.

In a word, blended learning is considered a priority direction of learning in modern educational conditions and creates unlimited opportunities for teachers and students. Blended learning allows you to optimize the teacher's teaching time and increase the effectiveness of teaching.

At the same time, the student becomes an active participant in the educational process and has the opportunity to form an individual educational trajectory based on their needs. This is a great help in preparing competitive professionals in today's environment. In these wet days, when globalization and climate change threaten the future of mankind, most of our students and knowledge-hungry young people stay at home and receive blended (distance) learning, it will not be an exaggeration if they effectively use elements of education and e-learning and develop learning.

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PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE AS A KEY FACTOR OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract.

The problem of professional training of a foreign language teacher is a comprehensive problem of the theory and practice of pedagogical education, since it, in essence, goes to the problem of forming the personality of a professional teacher. This article reveals some problems of professional competence as a key factor of foreign language teaching.

Keywords.

competence, cooperation, professional development, foreign language learning and teaching.

Introduction.

Modern processes of globalization and integration of the Republic of Uzbekistan into the world space, ongoing economic reforms, active cooperation of our state with foreign countries have led to the fact that the importance of a foreign language is becoming not only an effective factor in the socio-economic, scientific, technical and general cultural progress of society, but also a condition effective innovative activity of modern man.

In this context, it seems relevant to address the problem of training a specialist within a limited educational period, capable of intercultural interaction in a particular professional field and acquiring individual experience of communicating with representatives of a different culture.

Main part: An important role in the foreign language training of the future specialist is given to the high professional culture of the teacher. In the modern sense, the professional culture of a technical university teacher is a complex integral characteristic of his/her social, professional and personal qualities, reflecting the level of his professional knowledge, skills and experience in organizing productive interaction with students to achieve a socially valuable result in specific conditions of professional and educational activities [8,157].

Productive interaction with students is a prerequisite for the successful implementation of the process of foreign language learning. The teaching of a foreign language is based on teaching its practical mastery, the formation and development of the student's communicative competence. The desire of students to master a foreign language is directly related to the professional and personal qualities of the teacher, his/her ability to interest his subject [27, 17].

At the same time, a productive dialogue with the teacher is the main form of introducing students to oral speech in a foreign language.

As long-term practice shows, motivation is a necessary condition for successful foreign language communication and the main prerequisite for mastering a foreign language. The desire to learn the language contributes to the stimulation of the thinking process of students, the formation of a sustainable desire to acquire knowledge, which in turn directly affects the effectiveness of the learning process.

Our own experience of teaching foreign languages, German at a technical university indicates that currently students have low motivation to learn a foreign language. The main reasons for this are: the presence of an initially lower level of formation of communicative skills compared to their peers, who preferred activities in the "person-to-person" system [38, 59], the perception of a foreign language as a complex subject that requires a lot of effort, time and perseverance; disbelief in one's own strengths; unwillingness to overcome the difficulties that arise in the process of learning a foreign language, etc.

In this regard, in our opinion, the manifestation of pedagogical assistance is productive through:

The implementation of the principle "do no harm" in the process of conducting practical classes;

Focus on the student's ability to independently overcome obstacles; reliance on the potential of the individual and faith in them; implementation of support for the desire of the student; benevolence;

Group activities, assistance, co-creation, approval, cooperation; reflexive-analytical approach to the process and result of activity. Many students, especially those who are just starting to study at a technical university, need contact with a teacher who can captivate them with their subject and give good advice: how to study correctly and effectively, how to rationally prepare for classes and allocate time, how to show the best of personal qualities constantly improve them, self-develop.

The success of interaction between a student and a teacher in this case largely depends on the professionalism of the latter, his professional culture [3, 171].

A significant role in the process of teaching a foreign language is played by the personal qualities of the teacher (charisma, pedagogical erudition, attentiveness, sensitivity (especially to those with poor progress), objectivity, etc.), who, acting in the classroom as a speech partner, should be able to create an atmosphere of confidence and comfort, contributing to the emancipation of students, overcoming the language barrier and a sense of insecurity.

Psychological assistance to students and exactingness towards them do not contradict each other, but we should not forget that excessive exactingness can become a demotivating factor. Some students perceive the disapproving attitude of the teacher as a personal tragedy, and, as a result, the positive motivation to study in this subject falls. In this context, the teacher needs to strive for non-evaluative technologies (for example, self-evaluation by which the student himself will determine the level of his progress, his success) [8,160].

At the same time, it is important to orient future specialists to the result of their training - competencies (knowledge, skills, personal characteristics and qualities), which should be formed in the educational process. Thanks to pedagogical skills, as well as love for the subject, the teacher is able to encourage students to fruitfully master a foreign language, while making the process of teaching a foreign language exciting and entertaining. One of the means of increasing motivation for learning a foreign language and removing the language barrier is the organization and participation of students in international programs, country studies projects, scientific and technical conferences on a foreign language. These activities not only increase students' motivation to learn a foreign language, but also contribute to the development of such skills as presentation, teamwork, interactive interaction with representatives of a different culture, which are necessary for a specialist in the future for effective professional communication [25,138]. To prepare competent professionals who speak a foreign language, the teacher must be competent him/herself and constantly improve his/her professional skills.

In recent years, the computerization of the process of teaching foreign languages has provided wide access to electronic dictionaries, learning sites and a variety of interactive learning programs [27, 14]. The introduction of innovative technical means into the educational process increases the level and quality of foreign language training of future specialists, opens up universal forms of

professional education, focused on the individual needs of an individual student and his specialization. At the same time, they also complicate the activities of the teacher, who needs to have the skills to work with software tools, be able to correctly integrate them into the educational process and reasonably combine them with live ("face to face") interaction between the student and the teacher in the classroom. The implementation of a successful learning process, therefore, is impossible without a creative approach to professional activity [18, 3518].

Pedagogical creativity is understood as a process of solving pedagogical problems in constantly changing circumstances. It is characterized by the introduction of certain methodological modifications into educational activities, the rationalization of teaching methods and techniques without any break in the pedagogical process.

The experience of pedagogical creativity is acquired in the conditions of a systematic search and solution of pedagogical problems [38,148]. The professional culture of a teacher is a phenomenon that requires not only constant development, improvement, but also reflection. Reflective activity in the course of teaching a foreign language helps the subjects of this process to realize their attitude to the interaction, to know the emotional state and the successes achieved, to evaluate their participation in the joint communication process. Thanks to reflection, the teacher's consciousness should be directed to comprehending what is happening, assessing and building his behavior in accordance with the nature of the pedagogical situation.

At the same time, reflection is an important mechanism for a person to get out of the current situation over the situational one, which makes it possible to predict the most productive behavioral strategies, taking into account their own goals of activity and the goals of other participants in the pedagogical process.

Conclusion:

The success of mastering a foreign language depends largely on the teacher's ability to understand the personal and behavioral characteristics of students, adequately respond to their actions, choose the appropriate system of teaching methods that take into account the individuality of students, on how well the teacher is fluent in a foreign language, demonstrates passion for his/her subject, developed pedagogical thinking, intuition, moral and aesthetic attitude to life, strong will and deep conviction.

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